

Cumulative Impacts of Multiple Municipal Water Withdrawals on Estuarine Salinity Dynamics: A Case Study in the James River

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Abstract: This report evaluates the potential impacts of proposed municipal water withdrawals on salinity and saltwater intrusion in the James River, VA, USA. A high-resolution SCHISM model was developed with local grid refinement at existing and proposed Hopewell Water Treatment Plant (HWTP) intake locations. Simulations under multiple withdrawal scenarios indicate that while water level changes are negligible, salinity increases are measurable in the oligohaline zone during low flow conditions. A single intake of 40 MGD produces an increase of ~0.1 psu, while combined withdrawals of 88 MGD (~1.3% of mean discharge) raise salinity by ~0.2 psu. Although these changes appear modest, they demonstrate that cumulative withdrawals can significantly erode the freshwater discharge that provides natural resistance against saltwater intrusion. The results highlight the importance of evaluating intake projects collectively and considering long-term estuarine salinity dynamics in water supply planning.

Keywords: Saltwater intrusion; Estuary; Salinity; Water withdrawals; Freshwater; Surface Water; Management

1. Introduction

Saltwater intrusion is a critical coastal environmental issue in the era of sea-level rise, as elevated salinity threatens freshwater-dependent ecosystems and water supplies (Werner et al., 2013; Berger et al., 2019; Kirwan et al., 2024; O'Donnell et al., 2024). In estuaries, river inflow establishes the horizontal salinity gradient and provides the freshwater needed to resist saltwater intrusion, and reductions in freshwater discharge therefore accelerate the landward movement of salinity (Hansen and Rattray, 1965; Monismith et al., 2002; MacCready and Geyer, 2010; Lee et al., 2024; Ma et al., 2025).

Freshwater, however, is also a vital resource for municipal, agricultural, and industrial uses. Large withdrawals in tidal-freshwater reaches can diminish an estuary's ability to resist salinity intrusion and increase risks to water-supply security. Previous studies have extensively examined the roles of sea-level rise, reduced river discharge, and other human activities such as coastal groundwater pumping, channel deepening, and land-use change in shaping salinity dynamics (Werner et al., 2013; Bhattachan et al., 2018; Chant et al., 2018; Ralston et al., 2019; Lee et al., 2025). Yet the cumulative impacts of multiple municipal surface-water withdrawals on estuarine salinity remain poorly understood.

This study addresses that gap through a case analysis of the James River, where several proposed municipal water intakes could collectively alter freshwater discharge and salinity dynamics. The analysis explicitly incorporates municipal intake locations and withdrawal rates into the model grid. This approach enables evaluation of a realistic case in which freshwater withdrawals are applied directly within the Appomattox River, a tidal-freshwater tributary of the James River, reflecting the actual design and operation of proposed intake structures. This report documents the modeling approach and results used to evaluate the potential impacts of these withdrawals on salinity and saltwater intrusion.

Virginia American Water (VAW) owns and operates the Hopewell Water Treatment Plant (HWTP), which supplies water to the City of Hopewell and surrounding areas in Prince George County. A project has been proposed to replace the aging, frequently malfunctioning intakes with a new intake and low-service pump station to provide reliable drinking water. The HWTP

currently withdraws from the Appomattox River approximately one mile upstream of its confluence with the James River. The requested capacity of the new intake and pumping system is 40 MGD to account for raw water losses during desludging and clarifier cleaning operations.

In addition to the HWTP intake, two other municipal intakes have been proposed upstream in the Appomattox River: one in Prince George County (8 MGD) and one in Chesterfield County (40 MGD) (Qin et al., 2022). Collectively, the operation of these three intakes would withdraw up to 88 MGD of freshwater, equivalent to $\sim 1.3\%$ of the mean James River discharge ($\sim 285 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, Qin et al., 2025). The potential impacts of these cumulative withdrawals on salinity dynamics and saltwater intrusion require careful evaluation.

2. Model development and scenarios

The SCHISM (Semi-implicit Cross-scale Hydroscience Integrated System Model) was applied to simulate the Appomattox River and adjacent James River. SCHISM employs a semi-implicit time-stepping scheme within a hybrid finite-element/finite-volume framework to solve the Navier–Stokes equations, and uses a Eulerian–Lagrangian method to treat momentum advection (Zhang et al., 2016). In the vertical, SCHISM applies a highly flexible and efficient hybrid coordinate system (Zhang et al., 2015). The model domain covers the full James River estuary, including upstream and lateral freshwater discharges derived from the EPA Phase 6 watershed model. It has been well calibrated and previously applied to assess intake impacts for Prince George County and Chesterfield County (Qin et al., 2022).

The unstructured grid allows local refinement to 1–10 m resolution, enabling representation of complex shoreline geometry and engineered structures (Figure 1). For this study, the James River grid was refined to include the proposed Hopewell Water Treatment Plant (HWTP) intake as well as the two previously proposed municipal intakes for Prince George and Chesterfield Counties (Figures 1c–d). The existing HWTP intakes were also incorporated, allowing direct comparison of impacts between existing and renewed facilities (Figure 1e).

The proposed HWTP intake design has 1 mm slot openings with a maximum through slot velocity of 0.25ft/s and a 40 MGD maximum withdrawal rate. The proposed HWTP intake area is represented by 170 quadrilateral grid elements with the resolution of around 1.37 m (54

inches), and each intake screen (203 inches by 54 inches) is represented by 4 grid elements with the size of 50.75 inches by 54 inches (16 in total for the 4 intake screens; Figure 2). The water depth is set to be -12 feet MLLW at the intake area and the water column there is represented by 5 vertical layers. The bathymetry data for the Appomattox River were obtained from NOAA chart and the refined bathymetry data for the area around the proposed HWTP intake were provided by Gannett Fleming. With this high-resolution model grid, the model is able to simulate complex dynamics in the near-field of the intake. In the model, water is withdrawn continuously at the location of the intake, and the withdrawal rate of water by the intake was set to be 40 MGD (i.e., $1.7525 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$). The withdraw rate for each grid element representing the intake is set to be $0.10953 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ ($= 1.7525 \text{ m}^3/\text{s} \div 16$). The two existing HWTP intakes were each represented by 16 grid elements. A withdrawal rate of 11.1 MGD ($0.4863 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$) was assigned to each intake.

Figure 1. The James River model grid with high resolution near the vicinity of the water intakes. (a) The James River, (b) the Appomattox River, (c) grid near the Prince George County water intake, (d) grid near the Chesterfield County water intake, and (e) grid near the water intake proposed in this study, including the two existing HWTP intakes (indicated by square-shaped grid blocks) and the proposed HWTP intake (indicated by a rectangular grid block).

Figure 2. The grid designed for the proposed HWTP intake area. Each of the 4 functional intake screens (solid blue areas) is represented by 4 grid elements.

The hydrodynamic model was run for the year 2017, a low flow year. Two cases were defined to evaluate the influence of intake operations: Case “Normal” (no withdrawal) and Case “Withdrawal” (with intake). We conducted the following four hydrodynamic simulations:

Scenario 1: Baseline condition (no withdrawal).

Scenario 2: Withdrawal by the proposed HWTP intake (40 MGD).

Scenario 3: Withdrawal by existing HWTP intakes (22.2 MGD).

Scenario 4: Withdrawal by all three proposed intakes in the Appomattox River (88 MGD total).

Model outputs were analyzed to compare salinity distributions along the James River under high-flow (spring) and low-flow (summer) conditions. Time series of surface elevation, salinity, and tidal currents were extracted at the HWTP intake area for detailed comparison.

3. Impact of water intakes on hydrodynamics

As described in Section 2, four hydrodynamic scenarios were conducted to evaluate the effects of freshwater withdrawals. To assess the impact of the proposed HWTP intake and the cumulative effect of all three proposed intakes, we analyzed changes in water level, current velocity, and salinity between the baseline case and withdrawal cases.

3.1. Velocity, water level, and salinity at the proposed HWTP intake

Horizontal velocities at the surface and bottom were compared at a representative location near the proposed HWTP intake (Figures 3–4). Differences between the “Normal” and “Withdrawal” cases are evident, although changes remain localized to the intake area. A time series of water surface elevations was also compared at the same location (Figure 5). The withdrawal scenarios produced a slight decrease in elevation, on the order of millimeters, relative to the baseline. This indicates that overall natural transport remains the dominant driver of water exchange in the Appomattox River, and that withdrawals have only a minor effect on local water levels. Salinity time series at the HWTP intake are not presented because the site remained in freshwater conditions for the entire simulation period.

Figure 3. Time series of surface horizontal velocities at one location of the proposed HWTP intake area. (a) “Normal” Case (without the intake), (b-d) other three “Withdrawal” Cases, and (e and f) the elevation differences of the withdrawal cases and the normal case.

Figure 4. Time series of bottom horizontal velocities at one location of the proposed HWTP intake area. (a) “Normal” Case (without the intake), (b-d) other three “Withdrawal” Cases, and (e and f) the elevation differences of the withdrawal cases and the normal case.

Figure 5. Time series of elevations at one location of the proposed HWTP intake area. (a) “Normal” Case (without the intake), (b-d) other three “Withdrawal” Cases, and (e and f) the elevation differences of the withdrawal cases and the normal case.

3.2. Salinity and saltwater intrusion in the James River

Salinity differences between the “Normal” and “Withdrawal” cases were analyzed across the James River estuary. Both high-flow (spring) and low-flow (summer) conditions were considered. With only the proposed HWTP intake operating, the maximum difference in bottom salinity is approximately 0.1 psu (Figures 6–7). As expected, withdrawals reduce freshwater inflow and result in slightly higher estuarine salinity compared to the baseline. Under the cumulative scenario with all three proposed intakes in operation, the maximum difference in bottom salinity increases to about 0.2 psu (Figures 8–9).

Figure 6. Daily-mean bottom salinity distribution for Case “Normal” (without intakes) and Case “Withdrawal” (Scenario 2, with the proposed HWTP intake), along with the salinity difference between the two cases. Results are presented for a spring date when freshwater discharge is relatively high. Note the different colorbar ranges used for salinity fields and their differences.

Figure 7. Daily-mean bottom salinity distribution for Case “Normal” (without intakes) and Case “Withdrawal” (Scenario 2, with the proposed HWTP intake), along with the salinity difference between the two cases. Results are shown for a summer date when freshwater discharge was sustained at low levels (near the 10th percentile of river flow) for over a month. Note the different colorbar ranges used for salinity fields and their differences.

Figure 8. Daily-mean bottom salinity distribution for Case “Normal” (without intakes) and Case “Withdrawal” (Scenario 4, with all three proposed intakes), along with the salinity difference between the two cases. Results are presented for a spring date when freshwater discharge is relatively high. Note the different colorbar ranges used for salinity fields and their differences.

Figure 9. Daily-mean bottom salinity distribution for Case “Normal” (without intakes) and Case “Withdrawal” (Scenario 4, with all three proposed intakes), along with the salinity difference between the two cases. Results are shown for a summer date when freshwater discharge was sustained at low levels (near the 10th percentile of river flow) for over a month. Note the different colorbar ranges used for salinity fields and their differences.

4. Implications for water Supply and management

The modeling results indicate that while a single withdrawal project has only a modest impact on estuarine salinity (~ 0.1 psu increase for a 40 MGD intake), the cumulative effects of multiple municipal intakes can be more substantial. When all three proposed intakes operate together at 88 MGD ($\sim 1.3\%$ of the mean James River discharge), salinity increases of ~ 0.2 psu are observed. Although these changes remain below thresholds that would immediately compromise water quality at intake locations in the Appomattox River, they demonstrate that incremental withdrawals reduce the freshwater discharge available to resist saltwater intrusion.

These findings have several management implications. First, evaluating intake projects in isolation may underestimate risks; cumulative withdrawal scenarios should be considered explicitly in permitting and planning processes. Second, the influence of freshwater withdrawals on salinity is likely to be amplified under conditions of low flow or drought, when river discharge is already reduced. Third, the interaction with long-term drivers such as sea-level rise further increases the potential for upstream salinity intrusion.

By quantifying salinity responses to proposed intake scenarios, this study provides a technical basis for decision-makers to balance freshwater withdrawals with the need to maintain estuarine water quality. Establishing withdrawal thresholds that account for both current and projected conditions will be essential for ensuring resilient and sustainable water supply management in the James River and similar estuarine systems.

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